

MANAGEMENT OF ADAPTATION AND INTEGRATION OF MIGRANTS IN MIGRATION PROCESSES

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Abstract. *In this research work, we will use certain theoretical rules to clarify the semantic content of the terms “migrant adaptation”, “migrant integration”, “state adaptation policy” and “state integration policy” to a certain extent when forming a promising state policy on the adaptation and integration of migrants. We are talking about creating a theoretical and methodological resource that can be used. We believe that its use in the future will serve to further improve migration legislation, prevent the risk of errors in the formation of state migration policy and prevent many migration threats, primarily reducing the risk of crime, illegal migration, extremism and terrorism in the migration environment.*

Keywords: *adaptation, integration, adaptation, migration, state, politics, object, subject, social, cultural, tradition, value.*

INTRODUCTION

Often, researchers explain the goals of migrant resilience as follows: the need to reduce illegal migration; the need to prevent conflicts between migrants and local residents, or the elimination of the risk of the manifestation of extremism and terrorism in areas where migrants are mass. All this is true, but it is very indirect and cannot reveal the needs of the migrant in the adaptation and integration processes. To answer this question, it will be necessary to identify the object and active subjects of adaptation and integration.

MAIN PART

In terms of content, the adaptation (adaptation) process is multi-vector in nature. It distinguishes several types of adaptation: climatic (adaptation to climatic conditions of residential areas); political and legal (adaptation to the peculiarities of political and legal relations of residential areas); household (home regulation: provision of food, water, clothing, etc.); economic (adaptation to economic conditions); socio-cultural (adaptation to the socio-cultural environment of the receiving society); medical and biological; other types of adaptation [1].

No one doubts that the object of adaptation is the migrants themselves. However, it is important to understand which categories of migrants adapt to local conditions? In our opinion, transit (passing from the country in which he moved to another country. Example: went to Mexico and passed to the United States) almost everyone adapts, except for migrants, business travelers, tourists and some other categories. Even illegal migrants adapt, but their adaptation is mainly criminal in nature, which is a topic that is specifically studied.

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Adaptation subjects. According to our opinion, the main subjects of adaptation are the migrants themselves. Despite the fact that they are classified as objects of adaptation, at the same time they are the participants (acting subjects) of this process. It is the migrants who decide to move to another country and come to a new place of residence (ishash) who are first interested in quickly adapting to new conditions, and the result of adaptation largely depends on the will of the migrant and his ability to adapt to the new environment.

Other subjects of adaptation include:

- 1) state;
- 2) local government authorities;
- 3) local residents;
- 4) public and political organizations engaged in migration issues;
- 5) entrepreneurial structures;
- 6) the migration environment in the territory of the settlement, etc.

Each of the subjects listed above pursues its own goals in the adaptation process. The main goal of adaptation for the Migrant is to get used to the new environment in order to achieve the following results:

- 1) to act with confidence in a new environment;
- 2) stay in the territory of the settlement without conflict (living);
- 3) effective performance of work or other activities in accordance with the established purpose of entry into the country;
- 4) feel safe and share a sense of social belonging to the host society;
- 5) to achieve the specified goal of migration, for example, a certain capital (for labor migrants), to become a citizen of the country where he went (for migrants), etc.

Public policy in the adaptation of migrants.

We will cite the basic theoretical rules that we will include in the desired definition.

1. Migrants are the main subjects of the adaptation process. This means that all other adaptation entities, including the state, will play the role of their partners, that is, they will have to help them in the adaptation of new conditions. Hence, the phrase "immigrant assistance" should be important in determining the state's adaptation policy.

2. In general, any public policy is aimed at solving important social problems (in our case – these are migrants) in relation to large social groups, the activities of state bodies (in our case – adaptation of immigrants to new living conditions). This mental construct is also reflected in the desired definition.

3. Not everyone is involved in the process of forming and implementing state adaptation policies, only competent state bodies are involved.

4. The participation of civil society structures in the formation and implementation of public policy is important. We believe that the adaptation policy of the state should not be an exception. Taking into account the above, we form a definition in relation to the states that are interested in accepting migrants.

The state policy on adaptation of migrants is the activity of competent state bodies aimed at helping to adapt migrants to living and living conditions in the society that receives them, involving local governing bodies, public organizations and other subjects of civil society. In our opinion, this definition fully and accurately reflects the essence of public policy, allows you to formulate a scientific idea of this phenomenon. In it, the phrase state assistance implies the

possibility of applying a wide range of measures: political, legal, economic, socio-cultural, etc., including state and public services [3].

Adaptation includes subjects of state policy - state bodies authorized to formulate and implement migration policies. In Central countries, the policy of adaptation to the state is implemented on two levels: Central and regional. The policy of Central adaptation is carried out by competent state bodies. Regional adaptation policy-by competent state bodies of territorial entities.

The objects of State adaptation policy are: migrants (reversible and irrevocable), local governing bodies, community organizations, local residents, business structures and the local migration environment are told [4].

The purpose of the state adaptation policy is to regulate the processes of adaptation of migrants to the interests of socio - economic development of the country and its territories, ensuring the security of the individual, society and the state, compliance with the rights of migrants and citizens of the country. In our opinion, foreign citizens adapt to the period of residence and residence in the territory of emigration, until the moment when they return or receive the citizenship of the adopted country.

The adaptation scale of subsistence as well as most migrants in the early period is relatively low, with a significant improvement in adaptation to the new environment for them in later periods (excluding those living in ethnic enclaves). In this regard, we propose to include in the scientific dictionary the concept of “migrant adaptation scale” – the degree of its adaptation to living and living conditions. In this regard, it is necessary to distinguish two stages of adaptation stimulation: initial and scale(depth). In the segment of socio-cultural adaptation, we form the criteria for assessing its scale.

* Promotion of early socio-cultural adaptation:

1) to assimilate by migrants the language, history and legal framework of the receiving state to the extent that it allows them to communicate with local residents, albeit without assistance, with some difficulty; to carry out their activities without violating the legislation of the country; to treat the history of the receiving country and its inhabitants with respect;

2) ensuring the use of the social resources of the places of residence of immigrants and their families: medical, educational, sports, etc., in volumes and conditions regulated by regional legislation and legal acts of the territories;

3) to ensure access to state and public services on issues of residence, labor and other legal activities in the territory of residence.

* Promote large-scale socio-cultural adaptation:

1) advanced level of study of the language, history and legal basis of the state by migrants, which allows them to freely express their opinions in communication with local residents; comfortable living in the territories of entry, without violating the legislation of the host country; to show their commitment to state power, on the basis of a deep knowledge of the language, legal;

2) mastering the customs, moral and ethical guidelines, cultural values of the local population, which allow immigrants to acquire behavioral and communication skills that are not very different from the local population [5];

3) to get acquainted with the scientific, technical, cultural and sports achievements that the locals are proud of, to give migrants the opportunity to conduct large-scale conversations with representatives of the host society;

4) the acquisition of knowledge about the political system of the receiving society, social ties, to the extent that it allows the migrant to partially socialize to society.

In the two – level regulation of the adaptation process of migrants, it allows the state to implement flexible state policies in this direction: in some cases to pay attention to the basic (superficial) level of adaptation, in others-to the scale. A similar approach can be applied to other segments of the state's adaptation policy – domestic, economic, etc.

The object of integration is Migrants.

The subjects of integration are the state, local governing bodies, public organizations, business structures, local residents, the environment of immigrants in the settled areas.

Unlike the adaptation process, in which the main active subject is a migrant, and the state contributes to its adaptation, in the process of integration, everything happens on the contrary. In it, the state is the main subject of migrant integration: it determines legal norms and integration procedures, selects integration strategies, etc.

The rest of the subjects of integration, such as local governing bodies, community organizations, religious associations, media, business structures, local residents, etc., help the state in the integration of immigrants. Migrants, on the other hand, unite by accepting (or not accepting) the support of community organizations and religious associations, in accordance with the rules and procedures established by state and local governing bodies [6].

State integration policy.

On the topic of who should be considered the object of integration policy, disagreements did not stop in the scientific community until now. Let's outline our position on this issue. We believe that domestic migrants do not need to be united, because they are citizens of the host country and they only need to adapt to the conditions of the migration area, that is, master the local dialect, customs, etc., and it is not advisable to include among the objects of the integration policy of returning migrants. Obviously, it makes no sense to place them in the socio-cultural organism of the receiving society, since sooner or later they will leave the receiving country. In our opinion, for immigrants who have been in the migration area for a short time and have returned, it is enough to coordinate with unfamiliar living conditions at the level of initial adaptation, and those who have a relatively long period of time may require deep adaptation. Thus, of all categories of migrants, only foreign citizens and stateless persons strive to become citizens of the receiving country (irrevocable migrants). It is proposed to consider immigrants of this category as the object of the integration policy of countries.

The generalization of our theoretical positions on integration as a management process allows us to formulate the necessary definition in relation to states that are interested in attracting immigrants.

State integration policy is the activity of authorized state bodies to include foreign citizens (stateless persons) who decide to stay in the host country in the structure of political, economic and socio-cultural relations of the citizens of the host country in this activity with the involvement of local governing bodies, public organizations and other structures of civil society[7]. In our opinion, such a definition fully reflects the meaning of the state integration policy, reveals its peculiarities in the policy of adaptation.

The result of choosing integration strategies largely depends on the target expectations of integration. Some researchers attribute the integration of migrants to their inclusion in the general ranks of citizens of the country without significant differences from the local population. Others see the result of integration in the non-conflict coexistence of migrants and Indigenous people with

different cultural values and religious beliefs. Others are interested in immigrants settling in vacant areas with partial restrictions on their habitat. Fourth, migrants partially preserve the cultural values of the Societies of origin while adopting the core values and patterns of behavior of the culture of the host society. The fifth-will be implemented in the process of placement in self-regulation mode.

Based on the established target assumptions, the state chooses the appropriate integration strategies: in assimilation, multiculturalism, division, integration, self-regulation, prospective integration policies respectively, as well as the use of all the above strategies for migrant integration, the most important strategies can be considered as multiculturalism and integration strategies.

The strategy of multiculturalism implies the long-term coexistence of migrants and Indigenous people, the gradual convergence and mutual penetration of their cultures. This is the evolutionary path of integration. In our opinion, the strategy of multiculturalism worked very well when the influx of small and well-controlled immigrants came to Western European countries. [8]

Under these circumstances, the integration strategy (the adoption of a culture of a accepting society while retaining some of the fundamental values of the country of origin by migrants) is growing in the interest of politicians. This strategy provides for the integration of migrants within the framework of specially developed state and municipal integration programs. In modern countries, various integration programs are being developed and implemented: resettlement of migrants to the territory of the whole country, taking into account the inability to create migration enclaves; state assistance to mixed marriages, socio-economic stimulation of such families, as well as other programs of an integrated nature.

It should be noted that the integration strategy is free from many disadvantages of the multicultural strategy, but at the same time it is more expensive and requires more financial, material and other investments in the migration policy of the state.

CONCLUSION

Adaptation is necessary for the migrant so that he and his family members can get used to the new environment as soon as possible and achieve the goal. This is the semantic formula of the adaptation. So this is the basis for the formation of the necessary concept. Migrant adaptation is the process by which migrants adapt to the conditions of the host society, in which migrants seek to live in a new environment for themselves.

In integration policies, it is advisable to use all the strategies mentioned above. Each strategy should be applied differentiated, taking into account the size of the migration flow, the socio-economic characteristics of the regions of settlements and the targeted expectations from integration.

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